

METAL-MATRIX COMPOSITE

WITH SHAPE MEMORY EFFECT

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ABSTRACT

Cu-based shape memory alloys are a kind of functional materials that provide shape memory effect, pseudo-elasticity as well as high damping behaviour. Cu-based composite material which possesses shape memory behaviour has been produced by adding small amount (1.5 % by weight) of Al_2O_3 particles into the CuZnAl base metal. It was observed that the grain size had been refined. Differential scanning calorimeter measurement showed that the martensitic transformation is impeded by the addition of Al_2O_3 particles. The transformation temperatures of these materials are affected and hysteresis is reduced. Because of possession of high damping behaviour, they are suitable for applications where both high damping and good wear resistance are required.

Keywords: Cu-based composite, shape memory alloy, martensitic transformation, hysteresis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Shape memory alloys (SMAs) have been studied for more than a few decades not only because they are scientifically interesting materials [1-5] but also because they are important in applications [6-10]. The characteristics of SMAs are related to thermoelastic martensitic transformation which does not require long range movement. In the transformation, atoms are co-operatively rearranged into a new, more stable crystal structure without any change in the chemical composition of the matrix. Because no atomic migration is necessary, this transformation is time-independent.

Some specific behaviours of SMAs, such as Cu-based and Ni-Ti alloys, are superelasticity, shape memory effect and high damping capacity which are related to their structural transformation of

martensite. The superelasticity is characterized by a large elastic deformation up to 10% obtained by stress-induced martensitic transformation. The shape memory effect is related to reversible transformation while the high damping capacity is a characteristic for all the martensitic samples over a wide temperature range below the transformation temperature [11].

In the present study, attention has been focused on the production of a Cu-based metal-matrix composite with shape memory effect and the influence of Al_2O_3 particle on the transformation behaviour of Cu21.5at.%Zn11.0at.%Al SMA.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Metal-matrix composite (MMC) of nominal composition of Cu21.5at.%Zn11.0at.%Al had been prepared by adding 1.5 wt.% Al_2O_3 particles into the base metal using casting method. To obtain a homogeneous material, the cast specimens were diffusion annealed at 1123 °K for 10.8 ks. Surface layer of 2 mm thickness was then removed after the annealing process. The specimens were then hot deformed at a deformation ratio of 1/10 and later betatized at 1123 °K for 0.6 ks. They were quenched into a bath of water kept at 368 °K to avoid decomposition of the high temperature β phase into the equilibrium phase. The specimens were finally aged at 368 °K for 3.6 ks. Martensitic transformation behaviour of the specimens was studied using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) at a cooling-heating rate of 10 °K/minute. Microstructure analysis was carried out on an optical microscope and a JEOL JSM-T330A scanning electron microscope (SEM) operating at 25kV.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Microstructure

Figures.1 and 2 show the typical microstructures of the SMA without and with Al_2O_3 particles added. It can be observed that the Al_2O_3 particles mainly dispersed along the grain boundaries while some of them were located inside the grains. The grain size was found to range from 50 to 100 μm .

3.2. Shape memory effect

Figures 3 and 4 respectively show the thermal behaviours of the SMAs without and with Al_2O_3 particles. The transformation temperatures were determined to be: $M_s = 352$ °K, $M_f = 330$ °K, $A_s = 365$ °K, $A_f = 374$ °K, for the SMA without Al_2O_3 particles (type A alloy) and $M_s = 370$ °K, $M_f = 325$ °K, $A_s = 359$ °K, $A_f = 380$ °K, for the SMA with Al_2O_3 (type B alloy) where M_s and M_f , and, A_s and A_f are respectively the temperatures at which martensitic transformation starts and finishes, and reverse transformation starts and finishes. The differences between M_s and M_f , and between A_f and M_s are 12 °K and 22 °K for type A alloy, while for type B alloy 45 °K and 10 °K. The difference

between M_s and M_f for type B alloy is larger than that for type A alloy. However, hysteresis for type A alloy is wider than that for type B alloy.

Figure 1. Microstructure of Cu-based alloy with Al_2O_3 particles.

Figure 2. Microstructure of Cu-based alloy with Al_2O_3 particles.

Figure 3. DSC measurement of Cu-based alloy without Al_2O_3 particles.

Figure 4. DSC measurement of Cu-based alloy with Al_2O_3 particles.

4. DISCUSSION

Coarse grains in the Cu-based SMA are easily formed during the heat treatment process. Coarse grained Cu-based SMAs are brittle and prone to premature intergranular failure [12]. When Al_2O_3 particles were added to the SMA, the small insoluble particles assisted grain nucleation during casting and also inhibited grain growth during hot deformation at 973 °K and betatizing at 1123 °K. Hence, the type B alloy has fine grain size as shown in figure 2.

Because Al_2O_3 particles are not soluble in the matrix metal, the transformation temperatures should therefore have only been slightly influenced due to the change in chemical composition. However, the DSC results have shown some differences in both the transformation temperatures and the hysteresis for the two types of alloys. Several phenomena may have contributed to the change in transformation temperatures in the present study.

- a). The slight change in composition, such as Al and Zn, may significantly change the transformation. According to Ahlers [11], to a first approximation, the transformation temperature can be empirically represented as:

$$M_s \text{ (K)} = 2485 - 66.9 (1.355 \text{ at\%Al} + 1 \text{ at\%Zn})$$

Because of the sensitivity of the change in composition to transformation temperature, the M_s temperatures for type A and B alloys are not easy to be reproduced. Hence, only the differences between M_s and M_f , between A_s and A_f , and hysteresis of $A_f - M_s$ are considered as the influence of particles.

- b). Due to the thermal mismatch between matrix and Al_2O_3 particles, high density of dislocations is expected. The stress field of the dislocations can affect the nucleation of certain martensitic variants and therefore influence the hysteresis behaviour of the SMA. Generally, the transformation temperatures would be lowered [12]. The stress field can also influence the growth of some martensitic variants [13]. In addition, because Al_2O_3 particles are less deformable, a high stress field is induced during forward transformation which increases the stored elastic energy. The high stored elastic energy in turn resists further forward transformation. In a thermoelastic transformation, a local equilibrium in the front of transformation between driving force and stored elastic energy and irreversible energy is required so that super-cooling for the increase in driving force to balance the increase in stored elastic energy is needed [14]. Therefore, M_f temperature decreases, leading to an increase in $M_s - M_f$. During reverse transformation, the stored elastic energy promotes the reversion of martensite plates and hence lowers the A_s temperature.

- c). Similar to (b), the grain size also affects the transformation temperature. Miyazaki [15] studied the difference in the transformation temperatures of single crystal and polycrystal which were produced from the same ingot and found that the M_s temperature of the single crystal was about 20 °K higher than that of the polycrystal. The lower M_s temperature of the polycrystal is the result of the constraining forces from the surrounding strain. Since fine grain size leads to higher constrain force, transformation temperatures of the type B alloy are higher.

Neglecting the difference in compositions between the type A and B alloys, it is clear that the differences in transformation temperatures between them are mainly due to the stress field induced by thermal mismatch and undeformability of the Al_3O_2 particles and also due to constraining forces from grain boundary.

5. CONCLUSION

Cu-based metal-matrix composite with shape memory effect has been produced using a casting method. DSC measurement has shown that the martensitic transformation is impeded by the addition of Al_2O_3 particles. Because high internal stress field is generated due to thermal mismatch between matrix and particles, and due to impediment of Al_2O_3 particles to martensitic transformation, the transformation temperatures are changed and hysteresis is altered.

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